

Peroxy acid oxidation : A kinetic and mechanistic study of oxidation of aminobenzoic acids by peroxomonosulfuric acid

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The kinetics of oxidation of anthranilic acid and *p*-aminobenzoic acid by peroxomonosulfuric acid have been studied in aqueous medium in the pH range 0–6.4 at 308 K. The reactions are second order – first order each in peroxy acid and in aminobenzoic acid concentration at constant pH. The reactivity of different peroxy species in the oxidation, has been determined. A mechanism consistent with rate-determining nucleophilic attack of the amino nitrogen on the electrophilic peroxy oxygen has been proposed.

Studies relating to oxidation of aromatic amines by peroxidic, metallic and non-metallic oxidants have received a great deal of attention. Radical pathways have been reported in the oxidations by metallic and non-metallic oxidants¹. Oxidations by peroxidic reagents, however, have been shown^{2,3} to proceed by heterolytic mechanisms in spite of the fact that the peroxides are good sources of free radicals⁴. It was of interest to undertake the kinetic study of the oxidation of aminobenzoic acids by PMSA to see if a nucleophilic attack of the amine is general for amine-peracid reactions.

The present paper deals with the oxidation of aminobenzoic acids by peroxomonosulfuric acid (PMSA) in different pH. The relative reactivities of different peroxy species such as HSO₅⁻ and SO₅²⁻, in the reaction have been estimated.

Results and Discussion

The kinetics of oxidation of anthranilic acid and *p*-aminobenzoic acid by PMSA were investigated at 308 K. At constant [substrate], pH and μ, the values of *k*'₁ were found to be independent of the initial PMSA concentration. This indicates that the reaction is first order with respect to PMSA.

The rates of oxidation of both the substrates were measured at various initial concentration of substrate and are collected in Table 1. The plots of *k*'₁ vs [substrate] were found to be linear (γ = 0.999 for both anthranilic acid and *p*-aminobenzoic acid), and to pass through the origin showing that the reactions are also first order with respect to substrate.

The rate expression at constant acidity can be represented as

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMSA}]}{dt} = k'_2 [\text{substrate}]_t [\text{PMSA}]_t$$

where, *k*'₂ is the observed second order rate constant and *t* the total concentration. The variation of ionic strength using NaClO₄ was found to have negligible effect on oxidation rate. Radical trapping agents like acrylamide also did not have any influence on the oxidation rate (Table 1)

Table 1. Second order rate constants for the oxidation of aminobenzoic acids by peroxomonosulfuric acid

Substrate	10 ³ [S] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁴ [PMSA] mol dm ⁻³	10 ⁵ <i>k</i> ' ₁ s ⁻¹	10 ² <i>k</i> ' ₂ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
Anthranilic acid	1.68	4.32	2.82	1.68
	3.72	4.40	6.51	1.75
	7.44	4.43	13.9	1.87
	10.3	4.70	18.4	1.79
	7.36	17.2	12.7	1.73
	7.30	10.1	13.1	1.80
	7.29	2.36	12.9	1.78
	7.40	4.50	12.9	1.75 ^a
	7.52	4.28	14.4	1.92 ^b
	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	0.948	4.50	1.81
1.84		4.38	3.51	1.91
3.68		4.62	7.58	2.06
7.29		4.34	14.9	2.05
3.68		8.02	7.62	2.07
3.68		2.68	7.43	2.02

^a[Acrylamide] = 5.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, ^bμ = 0.5 mol dm⁻³

The reactions have been studied at different temperatures in the range 298–323 K, and the rate constants are reported in Table 2. From the linear Arrhenius plots of log *k*'₂ vs T⁻¹ (γ = 0.999 and 0.996 for anthranilic acid and *p*-aminobenzoic acid respectively), the activation parameters Δ*H*[#] and Δ*S*[#] have been calculated to be 45 kJ mol⁻¹ and -131 ± 1 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ for anthranilic acid, and 53 kJ mol⁻¹ and -104 ± 1 J K⁻¹ mol⁻¹ for *p*-aminobenzoic acid.

Table 2. Oxidation of aminobenzoic acids by peroxomonosulfuric acid at different temperatures

Aqueous medium, $[H^+] = 0.1 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[PMSA] = 4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Substrate	Temp K	$10^2 k'_2$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$
Anthranilic acid ^a	298	1.01
	308	1.87
	318	3.30
	328	6.25
<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid ^b	298	0.96
	308	2.06
	318	2.96
	328	3.90

^aAnthranilic acid = $8.09 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. ^b*p*-Aminobenzoic acid = $3.71 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

The kinetics of oxidation of anthranilic acid and *p*-aminobenzoic acid by PMSA has been investigated in the pH ranges 0–4 and 0–6.4, respectively. The rate data are summarised in Table 3 and the plots of $\log k'_2$ vs pH are shown in Fig. 1. It is observed that in both the cases the rate increases with increase of pH. Such an observation seems to be quite different from that made in the PMPA oxidation³ of aminobenzoic acids, where the pH rate profile shows two bell-shaped regions, one in the region of pH 0–3 with a rate maximum at pH ~1.3 and the other in the region 3–7 with a maximum at pH ~5.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log k'_2$ vs pH (A) anthranilic acid, (B) *p*-aminobenzoic acid

Table 3. Oxidation of aminobenzoic acids by peroxomonosulfuric acid at different pHs

Temp. = 308 K, aqueous medium.

Substrate	pH	$10^3 k'_2$ $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	$10^3 k'_2$ (Calcd.) $\text{dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$	
Anthranilic acid	0.3	4.21	3.62	
	0.70	9.03	8.8	
	1.0	18.7	16.9	
	1.3	34.2	31.1	
	2.3	94.3	130	
	3.14	169	186	
	4.06	268	200	
	<i>p</i> -Aminobenzoic acid	0.0	1.45	2.05
		0.3	3.59	4.09
		0.70	10.5	10.1
1.0		22.2	19.8	
1.3		38.2	38.1	
2.15		145	145	
2.92		271	384	
4.45	534	490		
6.42	583	494		

Rate law and mechanism: In the pH range studied, aminobenzoic acid exists both in neutral and protonated forms,

where, S stands for aminobenzoic acid ($H_2NC_6H_4COOH$) and SH^+ for protonated aminobenzoic acid ($N^+H_3-C_6H_4COOH$). In the structure of peroxomonosulfuric acid⁵, one proton is a sulfuric acid proton and the other is a hydrogen peroxide proton ($pK_1 = 9.4$). In aqueous solution since PMSA exists as HSO_5^- and SO_5^{2-} , the observed experimental results may be rationalised as

The rate law pertaining to these reaction steps is

$$\text{Rate} = \frac{-d[PMSA]_t}{dt} = k_1 [HSO_5^-] [S] + k_2 [SO_5^{2-}] [S] \quad (5)$$

where, $[PMSA]_t$ represents the total analytical concentration of PMSA and is expressed as

$$[PMSA]_t = [HSO_5^-] + [SO_5^{2-}] \quad (6)$$

The total analytical concentration of aminobenzoic acid, $[S]_t$, is given as

$$[S]_t = [S] + [SH^+] \quad (7)$$

From eqns. (2) and (6), we have

$$[\text{HSO}_5^-] = \frac{[\text{PMSA}]_t [\text{H}^+]}{K_1 + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (8)$$

and

$$[\text{SO}_5^{2-}] = \frac{K_1 [\text{PMSA}]_t}{K_1 + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (9)$$

From eqns. (1) and (7), we have

$$[\text{S}] = \frac{K_a [\text{S}]_t}{K_a + [\text{H}^+]} \quad (10)$$

Substituting eqns. (8), (9) and (10) in eqn. (5), we have

$$\frac{-d[\text{PMSA}]_t}{dt} = \left\{ \frac{k_1 K_a [\text{H}^+] + k_2 K_1 K_a}{(K_1 + [\text{H}^+]) (K_a + [\text{H}^+])} \right\} [\text{PMSA}]_t [\text{S}]_t \quad (11)$$

or

$$k_2' = \frac{k_1 K_a [\text{H}^+] + k_2 K_1 K_a}{(K_1 + [\text{H}^+]) (K_a + [\text{H}^+])} \quad (12)$$

The reported values of pK_a for anthranilic acid⁶ and *p*-aminobenzoic acid⁷ are 2.04 and 2.38, respectively. Using the reported values of K_a for both the aminobenzoic acids^{6,7} and reported value⁵ of K_1 for PMSA, a least-squares solution of eqn. (12) was done, and the values of k_1 for anthranilic acid and *p*-aminobenzoic acid are respectively found to be 20.2×10^{-2} and $49.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. For both the compounds the values of k_2 are small and negative and thus can be approximated to zero. The rate constants, k_2' calcd., obtained from eqn. (12) at different pHs are recorded in Table 3. The general observations of second order kinetics, high negative entropy of activation and insensitivity to radical trapping agents support the polar nature⁸ of the reaction. The high reactivity of HSO_5^- as evidenced from the high k_1 value, clearly indicates that the oxidation is favoured with the more electrophilic PMSA species. This reveals the electrophilic behaviour of peroxy species in the oxidation⁹.

It follows from the above discussion that the oxidation involves nucleophilic attack of the amine lone-pair on the electrophilic peroxy oxygen of the PMSA species, HSO_5^- , giving rise to a S_N^2 type transition state (I), which ultimately results in the formation of products. The nucleophilic behaviour of amine in the reaction is in agreement with the fact that peroxides act as electrophiles in reactions with electron pair donors¹⁰.

The formation of azoxybenzene-2,2'-dicarboxylic acid as the product of oxidation of anthranilic acid, in the present study, is supported by the work on the oxidation of 3-aminopyridine by H_2O_2 ¹¹, and Caro's acid¹². The formation of such a product has also been reported in the oxidation of *o*-aminobenzoic acid by PMPA³.

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A R grade. Conductivity water was used in the preparation of the solutions and as a reaction medium. The potassium salt of Caro's acid, oxone ($2\text{KHSO}_5 \cdot \text{KHSO}_4 \cdot \text{K}_2\text{SO}_4$) (Dupont Chemical Co.) was used to prepare PMSA solutions. The concentration was checked frequently by iodometry, the self-decomposition being negligible in the pH region examined. The acidity was adjusted by adding appropriate amounts of perchloric acid or standard buffer (acetic acid-sodium acetate) and measured with a Digisun Electronics (DI-707) pH meter. Sodium perchlorate was used for adjusting the ionic strength. Both the aminobenzoic acids were purified by recrystallisation from water.

The kinetics were followed by measuring the rate of disappearance of peroxy acid, the estimation of which was done iodometrically using standard thiosulfate. The observed second order rate constant (k_2' obs.) was calculated by dividing pseudo-first order rate constant by the substrate concentration. The rate constants were reproducible to $\pm 5\%$. The temperature was constant within $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Product study : To PMSA ($5.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}$) dissolved in water (50 ml) containing HClO_4 (0.1 mol dm^{-3}), was added anthranilic acid ($1.036 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}$). The mixture was stirred and allowed to stand overnight at 308 K. The product, extracted with diethyl ether, was identified as azoxybenzene-2,2'-dicarboxylic acid (m.p. 516 K, uncorrected).

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